

RELIABILITY ESTIMATION OF BURIED PIPELINES USING FIRST ORDER RELIABILITY METHOD

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SUMMARY: Corrugated polyethylene (PE) pipes are used widely and have characteristic to resist environmental stresses from chemical and biological agents. Since the corrugated PE pipes provide substantial benefits over concrete, metal and other traditional pipes. Furthermore they are easy to install, tough in the field, durable in service and environmentally benign. In this paper, the limit state function (LSF) is formulated in accordance with conventional design method. The FORM (first order reliability method) is utilized to extract useful technical information in carrying out the effective design procedure for corrugated PE pipe. Using the three design criteria and failure probability, the methodology for reliability estimation of corrugated PE pipe is investigated. The effects of varying design parameters on failure probability are systematically studied. For three design criteria, it is found that the bending stress design criterion shows the smallest failure probability and the deflection design criterion shows the largest failure probability for varying design parameters. It is recognized that the failure probability increases with growing of the COV of random variables. It is also noted that the design parameters such as burial depth, modulus of soil reaction, outside diameter, pipe stiffness, soil density and distance to neutral surface must be selected properly to target a required safety level.

KEYWORDS: Corrugated Polyethylene (PE) Pipe, FORM (first order reliability method), Limit State Function (LSF), Failure Probability, Reliability Index, Target Reliability.

INTRODUCTION

Corrugated polyethylene (PE) pipes are extensively used for collection and transmission of fluids in aggressive environments over long periods of time. PE resin has the properties necessary to resist environmental stresses from chemical and biological agents. Corrugated PE pipes are lightweight and the corrugations provide wall stiffness and resistance to handling stresses, resulting in easy installation and lower labor costs.

Over the past thirty years, corrugated PE pipes have proven itself to be a strong, chemically inert and viable pipe for use in applications around the world. The excellent hydraulic flow characteristics and unparalleled abrasion and chemical resistance of PE pipes offer its users low operating costs and decades-long pipe service. Furthermore, the corrugated PE pipe provides substantial benefits over concrete, metal and other traditional pipes, since it is easy to install, tough in the field, durable in service and environmentally benign.

The corrugated PE pipe can, thus, be expected a long life with proper design, installation and operation. The design procedure of corrugated PE pipe includes the evaluation of deflection, bending stress and bending strain. This procedure establishes limits for each parameter. The parameters that are used in conventional design methods for corrugated PE pipe are

considered to be deterministic. But, in reality, uncertainties are found to be associated with these parameters. To take this into consideration, it is rational to employ a probabilistic method of analysis and design [1,2,3].

In this paper, the limit state function (LSF) is formulated in accordance with conventional design methodology. And the FORM (first order reliability method), which is one of probabilistic methods, is applied to design methodology of corrugated PE pipe and the corresponding failure probabilities are estimated. The reliability of corrugated PE pipe is assessed in terms of the value of the failure probability. The effects of design parameters on failure probability are systematically investigated by using a failure probability model for the corrugated PE pipe. Moreover, using the target safety level, the limitation of design parameters has been investigated.

DESIGN METHODOLOGY

The pipe behavior under varying boundary conditions can be broadly classified as flexible or rigid, depending on how it performs when installed. The flexible pipe such as the corrugated PE pipes can move, or deflect, under loads without structural damage. The rigid pipe is sometimes classified as pipes that cannot deflect significantly without structural distress such as cracking. The reinforced and non-reinforced concrete pipes are good examples.

The design procedure for corrugated PE pipe meeting the American Association of State Highway and Transportation Officials (AASHTO) M252, M294 and MP7 used in non-pressure applications evaluates deflection, bending stress and bending strain.

Deflection

The deflection is the change in inside diameter of a pipe when a load is applied to a flexible pipe. When deflections are small, as in most pipe installations, the reduction in vertical diameter is approximately the same as the increase in horizontal diameter. In pipe design, it is the vertical dimension that is usually of more concern. The vertical deflection is usually limited to 7.5% of the base inside diameter [4]. The base inside diameter is the nominal diameter less manufacturing and out-of-roundness tolerances inherent to the manufacturing process. This level of deflection is highly conservative and still provides a safety factor of approximately 3 against reverse curvature. This limit is also used in the design of other thermoplastic pipes and has been incorporated into several product specifications.

The deflection of corrugated PE pipe can be calculated using equation as shown below [1,4].

$$\Delta y = \frac{1000 \cdot K \cdot (D_L \cdot W_C + W_L)}{0.149 \cdot PS + 0.061 \cdot E'} \quad (1)$$

where Δy is the deflection of corrugated PE pipe, K is the bedding constant, D_L is the deflection lag factor (=1.0 when the prism load is used), W_C is the prism load on pipe that is calculated by soil load, W_L is the live load such as vehicle load, PS is the pipe stiffness and E' is the modulus of soil reaction.

The soil load is calculated in this design procedure using the prism load, sometimes referred to as the column load, which is defined as the weight of the soil prism directly above the outside diameter of the pipe. The prism load is calculated using equation as shown below.

$$W_C = (9.8 \times 10^{-6}) \cdot H \cdot \gamma_s \cdot OD \quad (2)$$

where H is the burial depth to top of pipe, γ_s is the soil density and OD is the outside diameter.

Fig. 1: Schematic for prism and live loads

Bending Stress and Strain

An estimation of the bending stress and strain should be done to ensure that they are within material capability. For PE, it can be generally noted that the bending stress should not exceed 20,700kPa and the bending strain should not exceed 5%. The bending stress can be calculated using equation as shown below [1,4].

$$\sigma_B = \frac{2 \cdot DF \cdot E \cdot \Delta y \cdot y_0 \cdot SF}{D_m^2} \quad (3)$$

Fig. 2: Schematic for pipeline parameters

And the bending strain can be obtained using equation as shown below [1,4].

$$\varepsilon_B = \frac{2 \cdot DF \cdot \Delta y \cdot y_0 \cdot SF}{D_m^2} \quad (4)$$

where σ_B is the bending stress, ε_B is the bending strain, DF is the shape factor, E is the long term modulus of elasticity of polyethylene, Δy is the deflection that is calculated by eqn. (1), y_0 is the distance from centroid of pipe wall to the furthers surface of the pipe that is defined by $\{(D_m - ID)/2\}$, ID is the inside diameter of pipe, D_m is the mean pipe diameter

that is defined by $(ID + 2c)$, c is the distance from the inside surface to the neutral surface and SF is the safety factor that is defined as 1.5.

FAILURE PROBABILITY

FORM (first order reliability method)

The reliability of a component can be defined as the probability that the component meets some specified demands under specified environmental conditions. And the reliability of a structural component can be defined as the probability that the structural strength exceeds the applied loads. In order to avoid some computational difficulties in the evaluation of the probability of failure, the FORM utilizing the reliability index has been used in structural reliability analysis. It is initially assumed that every variable is normal distribution and the probability distribution is determined by its mean and standard deviation. The FORM method is denoted from the fact that it is based on a first-order Taylor series approximation of the LSF that is defined as below [5,6,7].

$$Z = R - L \quad (5)$$

where R is the resistance (strength) normal variable and L is the load normal variable. Assuming that R and L are statistically independent normally distributed random variables, the variable Z is also normally distributed. The event of failure occurs when $R < L$, that is $Z < 0$. The failure probability (PF) is given as below.

$$PF = P[Z < 0] = \int_{-\infty}^0 \frac{1}{\sigma_Z \sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left\{-\frac{1}{2}\left(\frac{Z - \mu_Z}{\sigma_Z}\right)^2\right\} dZ = \int_{-\infty}^{-\beta} \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left\{-\frac{U^2}{2}\right\} dU = \Phi(-\beta) \quad (6)$$

where μ_Z and σ_Z are the mean and standard deviation of variable Z , respectively. A new variable U is defined as $U = (Z - \mu_Z) / \sigma_Z$, Φ is the cumulative distribution function for a standard normal variable and β is the safety index or reliability index and can be obtained as below.

$$\beta = \frac{\mu_Z}{\sigma_Z} = \frac{\mu_R - \mu_L}{\sqrt{\sigma_R^2 + \sigma_L^2}} \quad (7)$$

Fig. 3: Process to determine the reliability index

Eqn. (7) can be used for the case when the system has the linear LSF. Actually, most real systems and cases have not linear LSF but nonlinear LSF. So for the case that the system has nonlinear LSF, eqn. (7) cannot be used to calculate the reliability index. Rackwitz and Fiessler proposed a method to estimate the reliability index using the procedure as shown in Fig. 3 for the case of nonlinear LSF. In this paper, we iterated the loop as shown in Fig. 3 to determine a reliable reliability index until it converges to a desire value ($\Delta\beta \leq 0.001$) [6,7].

LSF (limit state function)

The LSF must be defined to formulate the FORM to evaluate the reliability. The three LSFs can be defined using the formula for calculating the deflection, bending stress and bending strain utilized as a design criteria, as below for deflection ($Z_{\Delta y}$), bending stress (Z_{σ_B}) and bending strain (Z_{ε_B}), respectively.

$$Z_{\Delta y} = 7.5 - \frac{\Delta y \cdot 100}{ID} = 7.5 - \frac{1000 \cdot K \cdot (D_L \cdot W_C + W_L) \cdot 100}{(0.149 \cdot PS + 0.061 \cdot E') \cdot ID} \quad (8)$$

$$Z_{\sigma_B} = 20700 - \sigma_B = 20700 - \frac{2 \cdot DF \cdot E \cdot \Delta y \cdot y_0 \cdot SF}{D_m^2} \quad (9)$$

$$Z_{\varepsilon_B} = 0.05 - \varepsilon_B = 0.05 - \frac{2 \cdot DF \cdot \Delta y \cdot y_0 \cdot SF}{D_m^2} \quad (10)$$

The event of failure occurs when LSF is smaller than zero and the failure probability can be calculated accordingly.

TARGET RELIABILITY

When the structural reliability analysis is needed to be carried out, a target safety level in a given reference time period and reference length of pipe should be selected and the target safety levels have to be met in design characteristics in order to ensure that a certain safety level is always achieved. The target safety level for buried pipelines is generally defined in the same level as for the intact pipeline. The target failure probabilities from the DNV Rules are reproduced in Table 1. In this paper, the target failure probability for satisfying the target safety level is adopted as $PF^T = 10^{-2}$ arbitrarily, because the corrugated PE pipe is not necessary to be high safety level [8].

Table 1: Target failure probabilities (PF^T) and varying Limit States for buried pipelines

Limit States	Safety Classes		
	Low	Normal	High
SLS(service-ability limit state)	$PF^T = 10^{-2}$	$PF^T = 10^{-3}$	$PF^T = 10^{-3}$
ULS(ultimate limit state)	$PF^T = 10^{-3}$	$PF^T = 10^{-4}$	$PF^T = 10^{-5}$
FLS(fatigue limit state)	$PF^T = 10^{-3}$	$PF^T = 10^{-4}$	$PF^T = 10^{-5}$
ALS(accident-al limit state)	$PF^T = 10^{-4}$	$PF^T = 10^{-5}$	$PF^T = 10^{-6}$

CASE STUDY

The random variables listed in Table 2 have been utilized to estimate the probability of failure and to assess the reliability of the corrugated PE pipe. The live load is negligible when the burial depth to top of pipe is 7.6m [1,3].

The coefficient of variation (COV) is defined as below.

$$COV = \frac{\sigma_x}{\mu_x} \quad (11)$$

where σ_x is the standard deviation of random variable X and μ_x is the mean of random variable X .

Table 2: Random variables and their statistical values

Variable	Mean	COV	Variable	Mean	COV
K	0.1	-	γ_s (kg/m ³)	1,766	0.01
D_L	1.0	-	OD (mm)	866	0.08
PS (kPa)	193	0.01	DF	4.9	0.02
E' (kPa)	13,800	0.06	E (kPa)	151,700	0.06
H (m)	7.6	0.05	ID (mm)	755	0.08
SF	1.5	-	c (mm)	34.29	0.05

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using variables in Table 2, the failure probability is calculated for each design criterion to estimate the reliability of corrugated PE pipe. The reliability of corrugated PE pipe is also assessed using failure probability and the limitation of design parameters selected in accordance with target safety level. This limitation may be used in design procedure to perform the design of corrugated PE pipe economically.

Fig. 4: Relationship of failure probability versus burial depth and modulus of soil reaction for three design criteria

The relationship between failure probability and various burial depth and modulus of soil reaction for three design criteria is shown Fig. 4. It is noted that the failure probability increases with growing the burial depth and the failure probability decreases with growing the

modulus of soil reaction. It is found from Fig. 4 that the increasing rate of failure probability for deflection and bending strain criteria increases has steep after the burial depth is about 6m. And the failure probability of deflection and bending strain criterion decreases rapidly when the modulus of soil reaction is about 16,000kPa. And the deflection criterion is found to show the largest failure probability. However, the bending stress criterion shows the smallest failure probability, that is, the bending stress criterion tends to be highly conservative design. The target failure probability is represented with a line located at failure probability of 10^{-2} in each figure. With this target safety level, we can assess the safety of corrugated PE pipe. If the failure probability estimated for corrugated PE pipe is smaller than the target safety level, it may be assumed that the corrugated PE pipe is safe. On the other hand, the corrugated PE pipe is unsafe, if the failure probability is larger than the target safety level.

Table 3: Safety ranges to satisfy the target safety level of $PF^T = 10^{-2}$

	Deflection	Bending Stress	Bending Strain
Burial Depth (below, m)	6.8	Over 12	7
Modulus of Soil Reaction (above, kPa)	15700	Under 11000	15000
Outside Diameter (below, mm)	780	Over 1200	810
Pipe Stiffness (above, kPa)	400	Under 100	310
Soil Density (below, kg/m^3)	1600	Over 2000	1650
Distance to neutral surface (below, mm)	—	Over 50	35

Table 3 shows the range of safety for various parameters in the corrugated PE pipe design procedure when a safety level of $PF^T = 10^{-2}$ is targeted. Using the data in Table 3, the limitation of design parameters for corrugated PE pipe can be estimated according to the three design criteria. The data shown in Table 3 may be utilized for design procedure to ensure reliability of corrugated PE pipe or to predict the safety of the corrugated PE pipe.

Figure 5 shows the relationship between failure probability and various outside diameter and pipe stiffness for three design criteria. It is found from Fig. 5 that the failure probability increases with bigger outside diameter of corrugated PE pipe, and the failure probability decreases with the larger pipe stiffness. The deflection criterion shows the largest failure probability and the bending stress criterion shows the smallest failure probability. The increasing rate of failure probability for outside diameter becomes steep, when the outside diameter is larger than approximately 700mm. And the decreasing rate of failure probability for pipe stiffness becomes moderate, when the pipe stiffness is larger than approximately 450kPa.

The line located at 10^{-2} of failure probability in Fig. 5 indicates the target safety level. When the target safety level of $PF^T = 10^{-2}$ is considered, the range of outside diameter and pipe stiffness for safety of the corrugated PE pipe is shown in Table 3 for three design criteria.

The variation of failure probability with various soil densities and distances from outside surface to neutral surface is shown in Fig. 6. Because the distance from outside surface to neutral surface is not design parameter in the deflection design criterion, the variation of failure probability is not studied in Fig. 6. It is recognized from Fig. 6 that failure probability increases with the larger soil density and distance to neutral surface. The deflection design criterion shows the largest failure probability and the bending stress design criterion shows the smallest failure probability for varying soil densities. For varying distances from outside surface to neutral surface, the failure probability of bending strain design criterion is larger than that of bending stress. It is noted that the failure probability increases steeply, when the soil density is larger than about 1500kg/m^3 .

Fig. 5: Relationship of failure probability versus outside diameter and pipe stiffness for three design criteria

Fig. 6: Relationship of failure probability versus soil density for three design criteria and distance from outside surface to neutral surface for two design criteria

The range of soil density and distance from outside surface to neutral surface for safety of the corrugated PE pipe is shown in Table 3 for three design criteria, when the target safety level of $PF^T = 10^{-2}$ is considered.

Figure 7 shows the relationship between the failure probability and COV of random variables for three design criteria. A larger COV means a more scattered distribution of random variables around the mean value. It is recognized that the failure probability increases with growing the COV of random variables. For the deflection design criterion, the scattering of the data for outside diameter, burial depth, soil density and modulus of soil reaction affect the failure probability significantly. For the bending stress design criterion, the scattering of the data for soil density, burial depth and outside diameter affect the failure probability significantly, however on the other hand, the scattering of the data for pipe stiffness, modulus of soil reaction and distance from neutral surface don't influence significantly on the failure probability. For the bending strain design criterion, the effects of the scattering of data for modulus of soil reaction on failure probability are the largest and the effects of the scattering of data for pipe stiffness on failure probability are the smallest, respectively.

The COV of outside diameter and distance from outside surface to neutral surface are affected by environment of manufacture and the COV of burial depth, soil density and modulus of soil reaction are affected by environment of installation for corrugated PE pipe. So it is strongly recommended for the engineers who design the corrugated PE pipe to select an appropriate environment of manufacture and installation.

Fig. 7: Relationship of failure probability versus coefficient of variation (COV) for three design criteria

In this paper, the methodology for reliability estimation of corrugated PE pipe is investigated using three design criteria and failure probability. For three design criteria, it is found that the bending stress design criterion shows the smallest failure probability and the deflection design criterion shows the largest failure probability for various design parameters. That is, the bending stress design criterion shows high conservative design procedure. Therefore, the limitation of most design parameters must be chosen according to deflection design criterion. But, the limitation of several design parameters like distance from outside surface to neutral surface must be chosen according to bending strain design criterion, because the distance from outside surface to neutral surface is not design parameter at deflection design criterion. When the limitation of design parameters is chosen, the target safety level must be considered. And the limit values to guarantee the safety of corrugated PE pipe must be selected in the range of satisfy the target safety level.

CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, the FORM (first order reliability method) is utilized to extract useful technical information in carrying out the effective design procedure for corrugated PE pipe. Using the three design criteria and failure probability, the methodology for reliability estimation of corrugated PE pipe is investigated. Furthermore, the effects of various design parameters on failure probability and design to guarantee the reliability of corrugated PE pipe are systematically studied and the following results are obtained:

- (1) The failure probability increases with larger design parameters such as burial depth, outside diameter, soil density and distance from outside surface to neutral surface. On the

other hand, the failure probability decreases with larger design parameters such as modulus of soil reaction and pipe stiffness.

(2) For three design criteria, it is found that the bending stress design criterion shows the smallest failure probability and the deflection design criterion shows the largest failure probability for various design parameters. That is, the bending stress design criterion is turned out to be high conservative design procedure.

(3) It is recognized that the failure probability increases with larger COV of random variables. Because the COV of design parameters is affected by environment of manufacture and installation, the engineering designer must be advised to select appropriate environment of manufacture and installation to guarantee the appropriate scattering of data.

(4) It is noted that the design parameters such as burial depth, modulus of soil reaction, outside diameter, pipe stiffness, soil density and distance to neutral surface must be selected properly to target a required safety level.

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